

Ujrah On Qardh In Islamic Jurisprudence A Comparative Study

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Abstract

Many individuals and institutions charge Ujrah when they give Qardh. This raises questions about the permissibility of the ujrah in Islamic jurisprudence, particularly since all positive laws have approved its legitimacy worldwide. The paper attempts to answer this question in three sections. The first section defines the terms ujrah and qardh, the second discusses the permissibility of taking ujrah on qardh whereas the third one discusses jurisprudential control in relation to increase in the loan.

Introduction

Muslim jurists define ujrah as what that the leaser undertakes to pay in return for the benefit used. They set a criterion for the things that can be given as ujrah, saying that anything that serves as a price in a sale can be an ujrah in lease. Therefore, ujrah must be known in lease contracts. The Prophet (peace be upon him) said: "A man should inform the person whom he hires of his ujrah." Ujrah may take the form of payment that could be paid later, such as dirhams, dinars, and weighable, volumetric, and countable items. In this case, it should be defined in terms of its category, type, description, and amount. If the ujrah involves an element of uncertainty that causes dispute, the contract shall be invalid.

Ujrah in Fiqh terminology refers to the compensation the lessee pays to the lessor in return for the benefit contracted. According to the majority of jurists, it resembles the price in a sale contract. Malik scholars, however, name the compensation given for hiring a person or for movable items – except ships and animals – ujrah. On the other hand, the payment provided for renting non-humans, immovable objects such as houses and lands, or movable things like ships and animals – is called kirÉ.

Some scholars said that ujrah refers to the payment for the services humans offer, and kirAA´ refers to the cost of the benefits derived from non-humans. Sometimes they are used interchangeably.

An-Nafraawi said: "Ujrah contract is to contract on the benefits humans usually offer, and kiraa´ contract is the arrangement through which benefits of animals and houses are owned."

Concept of Qardh

Qardh signifies "giving money to someone as an act of worship for the sake of Allah the Almighty so that the recipient uses it then returns it or the like of it."ⁱ The money given is called qarġ; the giver of the money muqrġ (lender); and the recipient of the money muqtariġ and mustaqridh (borrower). Also, the money returned by the muqtariġ to the muqrġ is called badal al-qarġ, whereas taking money as a sort of qardh is called iqtiradh (borrowing). Many jurists refer to qardh as salaf, albeit they use the word salaf in the sense of salam contract.

Qardh has been legislated as an exception to the typical forms of contracts according to the majority of the Malik, Shafie, and Hanbali scholars. The rationale behind this exception is that qardh aims to benefit the borrower and ease their living conditions. That is why qardh entails a great reward from Allah the Almighty. He says: {There is no benefit in most of their private conversation, save in enjoining charity, or maaruff, or reconciliation between people. And whoever does that, seeking Allah's pleasure, We shall give him a magnificent reward} [Quran 4:114] The word *maaruf* here refers to any act that the Sharia approves and reason does not reject. Some scholars construe it to mean the qarġ and relieving the distressed. MuqÉtil said: "MaNrÉf in the verse means qarġdh."ⁱⁱ Ibn Al-JawzÉ said: "Maaruf has two interpretations. The first is qardh, and this is reported from Ibn ŃAbbÉs and MuqÉtil. The second covers all acts of righteousness, and this is the opinion of Al-QÉÉ Abu YaŃIÉ and Abu Sulayman Ad-Dimashqe."

Anas (may Allah be pleased with him) reported that Allah's Messenger (peace be upon him) said:

On the night I was taken on the Journey of Al-Isra', I grasped that it was written at the gate of Heaven: "Charity commands a tenfold reward and qardh entails an eighteenfold reward." I said: "O Gabriel! Why is a qardh more rewarding than charity?" He replied: "Because the person begging for money usually owns something to live on, but the borrower who requests qardh usually does so only because he is in real need."

Ibn Mas'ud (may Allah be pleased with him) reported that Allah's Messenger (peace be upon him) said: "A Muslim who lends qardh to another Muslim two times, it is as if he gives charity one time." Abu Ad-Dard' said: "I should give two dinars as qardh twice rather than give them away in charity. By doing so, the two dinars are returned to me, and I spend them in charity again so that I obtain two rewards."

Abdullah ibn 'Amr ibn Al-'As said: "I should grant a man one dinar as qardh, and when he repays it, I lend it to someone else rather than give it in charity. The reward for charity is written only at the time of giving it; however, the reward of qardh continues as long as it is with the borrower."

Therefore, qardh is an act of righteousness and should not be a means for gaining profits or investing the money loaned.

1. How Valid Is Charging Ujrah on Qardh in Sharia

Qardh is a contract of easiness and an act of worship. Demanding an increase in its repayment will lead to the disappearance of kindness among people. Allah the Almighty assigned for it an immense reward because the lender does not charge any interest on the compensation for qardh. Also, the borrower utilizes the money loaned till s/he repays it without increase.

Jurists have agreed that what is acknowledged by tradition resembles what is acknowledged by provision, basing on this: if gifts are traditionally acknowledged in a loan contract, it is forbidden; because it is a well-known increment in the loan, and on that, Ibn Nujeim quoted: "... and in the Bazaziah, that what is a condition by customs resembles that is legally a condition, including: If the borrower usually returns more than what he borrows, is it forbidden to give him a loan in a way of acknowledging his usual habit similar to a condition?... etc.", and Dr. Wahba Al-Zuhaili said that: "If the increase is based on a condition, a promise, or a custom, it is absolutely prohibited.

However, if the borrower paid extra money without being stipulated or being a regular habit, this increase would be lawful according to the Hanafis, Shafis, and Ahmad in one narration. The juristic rule states that actions are permissible by default. Abu Rafi' (may Allah be pleased with him) reported that the Prophet (peace be upon him) borrowed a young camel. When the camels of sadaqah came to him, he commanded Abu Rafi' to return the young camel to the man. He returned to the Prophet (peace be upon him) and said: "I have only found a great camel whose age is seven years." So the Prophet (peace be upon him) instructed him: "Give the camel to him. Indeed, the best person is the one who settles his debt in the best way." This Hadith indicates that it is permissible to take qarl and incur debt. The Prophet (peace be upon him) took qarl because he needed it; otherwise, he usually seeks refuge in Allah from debt.

Ibn Al-Humam, and Malik and Hanbal scholars hold that the extra money which is not stipulated is unlawful. That is to block the means leading to getting an increase in qarl. Also, the Prophet (peace be upon him) said: "Do not accept a gift from the person you give qarl." He also said: "Whoever gives qarl and is offered a gift or a ride from the borrower should accept the gift or the ride only if they used to do so beforehand."

The most correct is what those who considered the pretext of taking an increase in the loan forbidden, unless it is justified that the gift is not because of the loan but because of a good intention for example exchanging gifts being a custom between them before the loan or something that necessitates it, such as marriage and the like.

Attested to this is what Ibn Sirin narrated that Omar, may God be pleased with him, extended a loan to Ubayyi bin Kaab, may God be pleased with him of ten thousand dirhams, in paying back the loan, Ubayyi bin Kaab gifted Umar fruits from his farmland, and Umar returned them to him. Ubayyi approached him and said it is well known by all the residents of medinah that I harvested the best fruits and we also need nothing, so why reject our gift? Then gifted to him after that, and he accepted

Ibn al-Qayyim said: Umar's response was based on suspicion that his gift was because of the loan, when he was certain that it was not because of the loan, he accepted it and this is the basis for the closure of the dispute regarding the issue of the gifts on loans.

If the concept of good intent is not clear, it is forbidden except for the lender to count it from the debt, this is based on what Al-Athram narrated that a man gave a twenty dirhams loan to a fish seller, so he began to gift him fish until he reached thirteen dirhams in gifts. He consulted Ibn Abbas and he answered, "Give him seven dirhams".

Muslim jurists unanimously agree that the increase stipulated to be paid by the borrower to the lender is forbidden. They support this ruling by the Companions' sayings, consensus, and analogical reasoning.

It was reported that Ibn ʿAbbās (may Allah be pleased with him) forbade any qarḥ that accrues benefit. Ibn Al-Munḥir conveyed the consensus over this ruling, saying: “Scholars have unanimously agreed that if the lender stipulated an increase or a gift to be paid by the borrower and gave money on this condition, accepting such an increase would be usury.”

As for analogical reasoning, qarḥ has been legislated to facilitate man’s life and offer it as an act of worship to Allah. Requiring an increase in its settlement ignores these objectives. Al-Karkhī said that this ruling applies if the benefit is imposed in the contract. If the benefit is not stipulated in the agreement, but the borrower repays the loan in a better manner, this shall be valid.

Considering that the increase stipulated in the qarḥ contract is forbidden, Muslim jurists differed regarding the specification of a term for qarḥ. Most jurists do not accept setting a duration for qarḥ, whereas other scholars say it is permissible. Those who allow it to support their view by the generic evidence on fulfilling the promises. Scholars rejecting it substantiate their opinion by the fact that setting a term contradicts the essence of the qarḥ contract, particularly setting a period commands a part in the compensation. The money loaned should not entail any increase in its payment.

2. The Jurisprudential Control in Relation to An Increase in a Loan “Every loan that brings in a benefit is forbidden”.

This rule was stipulated by Ibn Nujaim in “Al-Ashbah and Al-Nazaer”, and Al-Mujadidi in “Qawa’id Al-Fiqh”. It was also mentioned in other books that deal with branches of fiqh.

Basing on that: The loan contract is invalidated by agreement stipulating an increase in its allowance, whether the increase is in quantity or quality, for example if the borrower returns more or better than what he took.; this is because the loan was prescribed and legalized with a characteristic of being gentle with the servants of God as well as drawing them closer to him, so if it is stipulated or known to increase, it goes out from the intention of the hereafter reward to the purpose of worldly benefit that is prohibited by law and referred to as usury/riba

so, by observing this rule, the position of the jurists towards preventing any increase in the loan becomes clear, and as a result rejecting all the economic theories that were said to justify the interest on capital

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